

HailTrack - Improving Radar-Based Hailfall Estimates by Modelling Hail Trajectories

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ABSTRACT

A spatial mismatch between radar-based hail swaths and surface hail reports is commonly noted in meteorological literature. The discrepancy is partly due to hailstone advection between detection aloft and observation at the ground. The present study aims to mitigate this problem by developing a computational model to estimate hailfall using radar observations. The model operates by detecting, tracking and collating hailstone trajectories using dual-polarised, dual-Doppler radar retrievals. Notable improvements in hailfall forecasts are observed when hailstone trajectories are considered, and initialising the model with hail differential reflectivity (H_{DR}) radar retrievals is found to produce the most accurate hailfall estimates. The analysis of a case study in Brisbane, Australia demonstrates that trajectory modelling significantly improves the correlation between hail swaths and hail-related insurance claims, increasing Heidke Skill Scores from 0.48 to 0.58. The accumulated kinetic energy of hailstone impacts also shows some skill in identifying areas that were exposed to particularly severe hailfall. Other unique impact estimates are presented such as hailstone advection information and hailstone impact angle statistics. The potential to run the model in real time and produce short-term (10-15 minute) nowcasts is also introduced. Model applications include improving radar-based hail climatologies, validating hail detection techniques and insurance claims data, and providing real-time hail impact maps to improve public awareness of hail risk.

1. Introduction

Hailstorms pose a significant risk to life and property in many parts of the world, resulting in over USD 1 billion in insured losses annually (Jewell and Brimelow 2009; Sander et al. 2013). The economic cost of hail damage highlights the need to develop capabilities to accurately quantify the spatial extent and intensity of hail impacts on the ground. The areal extent of hail swaths, in combination with hail intensity metrics such as maximum hail diameter or hail kinetic energy, form the basis of hail climatologies and hail damage modelling in the insurance industry (e.g. Kunz and Puskeiler 2010). Accurate hail swath information is also important for assessing the ability to detect hail by radar,

understanding hailstorm dynamics and microphysics, and verifying high-resolution numerical weather model predictions (Changnon 1970; Snook et al. 2016).

A review of hail literature reveals four common approaches for estimating the extent of hail impacts, namely: using hail reports (e.g. Zhang et al. 2008; Ortega et al. 2009; Allen et al. 2015; Kahraman et al. 2016; Allen and Allen 2016; Jin et al. 2017), *in situ* measurements such as hail pads (e.g. Changnon 1968; Auer and Marwitz 1972; Smith and Waldvogel 1989; Fraile et al. 1999), insurance claims data (e.g. Hohl et al. 2002; Schuster et al. 2006; Brown et al. 2015; Warren et al. 2019) and weather radar imagery (e.g. Basara et al. 2007; Cintineo et al. 2012; Ortega 2018). Issues such as population bias, reporting insufficiency and secular trends from population changes and

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reporting practices plague all of these data sources except those derived from weather radar (Allen et al. 2015; Ortega 2018). Estimates made from radars also benefit from fine spatio-temporal resolution, measurement homogeneity and the ability to measure in three dimensions. These benefits make radar-based hail impact estimates a compelling option for quantifying the footprint of hail events.

Despite the observational advantages of using radars to predict hail impacts, it remains a challenging task. Firstly, hail detection and sizing by radar is essentially an under-resolved problem as liquid water content, size and the number concentration of hailstones all contribute to a volume's back-scattering characteristics. This leads to a high level of uncertainty when using radars to estimate hail size distributions aloft (Depue et al. 2007; Wilson et al. 2009; Blair et al. 2011; Ortega 2018). Further uncertainty is introduced when radar-based hail retrievals are used to estimate the extent and intensity of hailfall on the ground (Schiesser 1990; Hohl et al. 2002; Schuster et al. 2006). Comparing radar measurements aloft directly to hail observations at ground level introduces two implicit assumptions: a) hailstone sizes remain constant from detection aloft until impact, and b) hailstones land directly below where they are detected aloft. This study aims to relax these assumptions by modelling hailstones from detection aloft to their expected impact locations. We expect this approach to significantly improve the skill of hailfall estimates, while acknowledging that the inherent uncertainty in estimating hail sizes with radar data places an upper bound on the potential accuracy of such endeavours.

Previous hail trajectory and impact mapping studies have shown that hailstones can advect considerable distances from their initial position aloft to their impact position on the ground, affecting the ability to match radar-based hail observations directly to ground truth (Schiesser 1990; Schmid et al. 1992; Conway and Zrnić 1993; Schuster et al. 2006; Hohl et al. 2002; Warren et al. 2019). Many studies use low-level tilts of volumetric radar scans to mitigate the effects of advection as hailstones at lower altitudes have less potential to advect large distances (e.g. Depue et al. 2007; Ortega et al. 2016). However, this approach is not suited for nowcasting purposes as it reduces the lead time for hail warnings and effectively extends the interval between subsequent radar measurements by omitting higher elevation tilts. Furthermore, the use of exclusively low-level scans is not feasible for vertically integrated hail retrievals such as Maximum Expected Size of Hail (MESH) and Vertically Integrated Liquid (VIL) (Greene and Clark 1972; Witt et al. 1998). To mitigate the effects of advection, many radar validation studies use a neighbourhood approach when matching radar-derived swaths to ground truth. This can involve matching hail reports to radar-derived properties anywhere within the spatio-temporal bounds of a storm (Blair et al. 2011; Ortega 2018), within a pre-defined radius around each hail report (Nanni et al. 2000; Cintineo et al. 2012;

Warren et al. 2019) or more complex methods based on the vertical reflectivity distribution (Ortega et al. 2016). The use of these matching techniques reflects the inability of current radar-based hail retrievals to adequately predict the spatial extent and location of hail swaths on the ground.

Previous research has also attempted to improve the point-to-point match between radar products and ground truth by shifting radar-based swaths horizontally to account for hailstone advection. This has been demonstrated to significantly improve the correlation of radar-derived swaths with crop damage (Schiesser 1990), hailpad impacts (Schmid et al. 1992) and insurance claims (Hohl et al. 2002; Schuster et al. 2006). Whilst this type of advection correction does improve damage estimates, its accuracy and applicability are limited. Firstly, assuming a constant advection displacement for the entire radar swath does not consider that hailstones with different terminal velocities and different initial altitudes will advect different distances. Secondly, these corrections rely on high resolution ground truth observations to derive a representative swath displacement vector. This technique is therefore not suitable for use in regions with limited hail observations or in real-time nowcasting applications. A study by Schiesser (1990) is an exception to the simple, uniform horizontal shift methodology. The authors account for the height of hail observations and advect hailstones with a constant horizontal velocity. A representative horizontal velocity vector for the whole storm is selected by optimising the correlation between radar measurements and hail-pad impacts. Once again, this method under-resolves the complexity of hail advection calculations by assuming constant velocities for all hailstones and constant wind speeds throughout each storm.

The model presented here (subsequently referred to as HailTrack) targets the aforementioned limitations involved with associating radar retrievals aloft to hail observations on the ground. We introduce a trajectory modelling approach that uses radar data to predict the expected fall positions of hailstones. The aim of this new approach is to improve current radar-based hail impact predictions by directly modelling the effects of hailstone advection and melting. The model's methodology is first outlined in Section 2. The results from an Australian case study are then presented in Section 3 and an evaluation using insurance data is given in Section 4. A summary of the findings from this study and a discussion of future research directions are provided in Section 5.

2. HailTrack Methodology

a. Overview

The radar-based model introduced by this study requires polarimetric radar data, dual-Doppler radar coverage and a representative atmospheric sounding for each modelled storm. Radar data are processed to retrieve hail and wind

information, and radiosonde data are used to create a representative thermodynamic profile (Heistermann et al. 2015). Radar-based hail detection and sizing techniques are used to estimate the initial positions and sizes of hailstones, and trajectories are estimated by allowing hailstones to interact with 3D wind retrievals. Hailstone melting estimates are coupled to the trajectory model to account for reductions in hailstone sizes and terminal velocities as they fall below the environmental melting level. All hailstones that reach the ground in the model are collated into a unique, advection-corrected hailfall estimate. Refer to Figure 1 for a visual representation of this process.

b. Hail Detection and Sizing

The trajectory modelling approach used in this study requires a radar-based hail detection and sizing method to initiate hailstone simulations. The requirement for each hail sizing/detection algorithm is to provide a domain-wide, numerically-continuous hail size and position in three dimensions.

1) HAIL DIFFERENTIAL REFLECTIVITY (H_{DR})

Following a review of hail detection literature, the only continuous, three-dimensional hail size retrieval is based on the Hail Differential Reflectivity (H_{DR}) parameter. This technique exploits geometric differences between raindrops and hailstones in free fall by identifying hail as a combination of high equivalent horizontal reflectivity (Z_H) and low differential reflectivity (Z_{DR}). The reader is referred to Aydin et al. (1986) for a detailed description of the H_{DR} parameter. Depue et al. (2007) presented an empirical relationship between the H_{DR} parameter and hail size using a collection of 86 hail reports. The approximate H_{DR} - hail size relationship inferred from Depue et al. (2007, their Fig. 5) is as follows:

$$d_{hdr} = \begin{cases} 0; & H_{DR} < 21 \text{ dB} \\ 0.03H_{DR}^2 - 0.37H_{DR} + 11.69; & H_{DR} \geq 21 \text{ dB} \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where d_{hdr} is the resulting H_{DR} -based hail diameter estimate in millimetres and all H_{DR} calculations are performed in native radar coordinates. H_{DR} values below 21 dB are assigned a hail diameter of 0 as the H_{DR} - d_{hdr} relationship in Equation 1 was developed using values above this threshold. The H_{DR} lower bound corresponds to a minimum d_{hdr} hail size estimate of 17 mm (to the nearest millimetre). This ‘minimum observable size threshold’ is applied to all hail retrievals in this study to ensure consistency between approaches. It should be noted that hailstones smaller than this minimum threshold may be large enough to cause crop damage but are unlikely to damage common building materials (Schuesser 1990; Marshall et al. 2002). Depue et al. (2007) noted a large standard deviation of 10.6

mm between hail reports and the hail size relationship introduced above. This highlights the uncertainty involved in estimating one-to-one hail sizes using the H_{DR} parameter. The small ground truth sample size used to calibrate the H_{DR} - d_{hdr} relationship also limits our confidence in the method. Despite these concerns, H_{DR} hail sizes have been noted to show skill in detecting the presence of severe hail and are unique in producing three-dimensional, continuous hail size estimates (Aydin et al. 1986; Nanni et al. 2000; Depue et al. 2007; Murillo and Homeyer 2019).

2) MAXIMUM EXPECTED SIZE OF HAIL (MESH)

MESH is a single-polarised hail detection algorithm involving a weighted integration of Z_H above the melting level to produce a two-dimensional grid of the maximum estimated hail size at the surface (1×1 km spacing in this study). Refer to Witt et al. (1998) for a full description of the MESH method. Two-dimensional MESH grids are not immediately applicable to this study as three-dimensional hail retrievals are required to initiate trajectories. To resolve this problem, MESH estimates are extended into three dimensions by linearly varying MESH values according to the corresponding vertical Z_H profile (in dB units, 0.5 km vertical grid spacing). The resulting three-dimensional MESH hail size estimate (d_{mesh}) is formalised below:

$$d_{mesh} = \frac{Z_H}{Z_{H,max}} MESH, \quad (2)$$

where $Z_{H,max}$ is the maximum reflectivity in the column. This formulation ensures that for each column, d_{mesh} is equal to the two-dimensional MESH value at the altitude with the highest reflectivity, while the d_{mesh} values below and above decrease proportionally to the vertical Z_H profile.

The accuracy of the hail size formulation described above is limited by two main factors: 1) Z_H does not vary proportionately to hail size as it is also influenced by hydrometeor geometry, liquid water coating and number concentration, and 2) MESH exhibits limited skill in estimating one-to-one hail size when compared to hail reports (Witt et al. 1998; Wilson et al. 2009; Ortega 2018). Despite these limitations, MESH does show skill in confirming the presence of severe hail (Wilson et al. 2009; Cintineo et al. 2012; Ortega 2018; Murillo and Homeyer 2019; Warren et al. 2019); and is still widely used operationally for hail detection even in areas with polarimetric radar coverage.

3) H_{DR} WEIGHTED HSDA HYBRID APPROACH

Fuzzy-logic algorithms have superseded the more empirical approaches previously used for hydrometeor classification algorithms (HCA). These techniques are better suited to hail detection as they provide a framework to handle the uncertainty involved in classifying hydrometeor types from radar data (Park et al. 2009). Hail is separated

FIG. 1. A schematic showing the physical process of hail advection that motivates this trajectory modelling approach. The image represents an idealised version of hail core advection due to a storm-generated wind profile, resulting in a spatially offset hail swath.

from other hydrometeor types in this study using a hydrometeor classification outlined by Dolan et al. (2013). The hail size discrimination algorithm (HSDA) is applied following the HCA classifications by dividing the ‘hail’ category into ‘small’ (<25 mm), ‘large’ (25 – 50 mm) and ‘giant’ (>50 mm) hail size classes. These size classifications are used throughout the text to ensure consistency in hail size nomenclature. For a detailed description of the HSDA method, refer to Ryzhkov et al. (2013a,b). HSDA hail size retrievals cannot be implemented directly in Hail-Track due to their categorical hail size outputs. Instead, H_{DR} retrievals are used to introduce a continuous hail size spectrum within each HSDA class. Hail sizes are varied proportionally to the H_{DR} values within each size class. Therefore, ‘small’ hail varies between 0 and 25 mm and ‘large’ hail varies between 25 and 50 mm. The ‘giant’ category introduces additional complexity due to the absence of a prescribed upper bound.

Accurately estimating the maximum hail size within an entire storm using radar data is a difficult task. MESH is commonly used operationally for this purpose despite the aforementioned limitations in estimating one-to-one sizes. In the absence of a more robust, radar-based maximum hail size estimation technique, we use a stationary 75 mm (~3") upper bound for all ‘giant’ HSDA classifications. For giant hailstones, the absolute size has a limited effect on the uncertainty of trajectory calculations; as large terminal velocities associated with giant hailstones limit the potential for advection in the presence of horizontal winds.

To confirm this, we consider the sensitivity of the model to the arbitrarily-chosen hail size upper bound by varying this predefined ‘maximum’ hail size in Section 4. The hail size classifications for this method are summarised as follows:

$$d_{hsda} = \begin{cases} 25 \frac{d_{hdr} - d_{S,min}}{d_{S,max} - d_{S,min}}; & \text{HSDA = Small} \\ 25 \frac{d_{hdr} - d_{L,min}}{d_{L,max} - d_{L,min}} + 25; & \text{HSDA = Large} \\ 25 \frac{d_{hdr} - d_{G,min}}{d_{G,max} - d_{G,min}} + 50; & \text{HSDA = Giant} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $d_{S,min}$ is the minimum d_{hdr} value within the ‘Small’ HSDA size class, and $d_{G,max}$ is the maximum d_{hdr} value within the ‘Giant’ HSDA class, etc. This approach should allow further size discrimination within each HSDA class as d_{hdr} theoretically varies proportionally with hail size.

c. 3D Wind Retrievals

Accurate trajectory modelling requires a realistic estimate of the three wind components within the hailstorm. This study follows the method outlined in Protat and Zawadzki (1999) by using dual-Doppler data to resolve the three-dimensional wind field. This method is similar to other variational, multi-Doppler wind retrievals (e.g. Scialom and Lemaître 1990; Chong and Campos 1996; Bousquet and Chong 1998), but uses a unique time interpolation technique and solves the anelastic continuity equation by combining upward and downward integration schemes. The reader is referred to Protat and Zawadzki

(1999) and Collis et al. (2013) for a complete description of this method. 3D wind calculations are performed in a Cartesian coordinate system with a horizontal resolution of 1 km and a vertical resolution of 500 m. The ground-based radars used in this study are not suited to sampling near-surface altitudes due to the effects of ground clutter and beam divergence at increasing range. As a result, the lowest altitude for the 3D wind retrieval is 500 m above sea level. In our implementation of the Protat and Zawadzki (1999) technique, a reflectivity-fall speed relationship is also applied to pixels identified by the HCA classification as hail. This is implemented to correct for errors in vertical velocities due to the suspension of large hydrometeors (Conway and Zrnić 1993). Regions with nearly collinear beam orientations between radars are discounted from the analysis due to the requirement for dual-Doppler measurements. We define these nearly collinear regions where the cosine of the angle between the two radar beams is greater than 0.95.

Three-dimensional wind fields calculated using dual-Doppler radar measurements contain gaps in weak echo regions and in regions with nearly collinear beam orientations. This presents an issue for hail trajectory modelling as a small portion of hail simulations may fall into regions with missing 3D winds data. When this occurs in the model, a gap-filling method is used to find a representative velocity value. In missing wind data regions, the vertical wind velocity is set to zero and the horizontal components are set to the mean horizontal velocity values in the cross section at the closest height level.

This technique ensures that all hailstones detected aloft do reach the ground if they do not melt completely.

d. Microphysical Considerations

Melting plays an important role in altering the terminal velocities of hailstones as they fall (Rasmussen et al. 1984). A melting process is implemented within HailTrack using the model presented by Ryzhkov et al. (2013a, hereinafter R13A). Hailstone mass losses occur due to thermodynamic processes such as sublimation and evaporation, as well as the meltwater shedding parameterization introduced by R13A. Thermodynamic environment variables used in the model are sourced from a representative vertical sounding profile for each individual storm. No hail growth processes are simulated due to the inability to accurately estimate environmental variables such as super-cooled liquid water content in real time using current remote sensing methods. Hailstone densities follow modelling experiments by Rasmussen and Heymsfield (1987) in assuming that density increases with size from small, low density graupel ($600 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) to large stones composed of roughly solid ice ($917 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). This size-dependent density function is given below:

$$\rho(d) = \begin{cases} 600 - 0.25d^2 + 17.61d; & d < 36 \text{ mm} \\ 917; & d \geq 36 \text{ mm} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the hailstone density. For a comprehensive thermodynamic description on the melting model used and its effects on hailstone terminal velocities, the reader is referred to the appendix material in R13A.

e. Trajectory Modelling and Collation

It is currently not possible to accurately estimate hail size distributions aloft using polarimetric weather radar information. Therefore, instead of attempting to simulate a representative size distribution, trajectories are initiated based on the maximum expected hail size within each grid box (MESH) or radar voxel (H_{DR} , HSDA). This approach captures the spatial distribution of the most damaging hail while avoiding any assumptions about hail distributions in the atmosphere. Initial maximum size estimates are based on the hail detection/sizing methods discussed earlier. The only forcing mechanisms for hailstone trajectories are gravity and drag from the 3D wind field. At every point along their trajectory, horizontal components of the wind field (u, v) are used as the horizontal hydrometeor velocity, and vertical velocities are the sum of vertical air velocity (w) and the terminal velocity (V_T). Therefore, the true velocity vector for hydrometeors as they move through the atmosphere is $(u, v, V_T + w)$. Using this velocity vector, positions at a new time step (n) can be calculated based on the previous step ($n-1$):

$$\begin{aligned} x_n &= x_{n-1} + u_{n-1}\Delta t \\ y_n &= y_{n-1} + v_{n-1}\Delta t \\ z_n &= z_{n-1} + (V_T + w_{n-1})\Delta t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where Δt is the time step. A time step of 10 s was deemed sufficient for avoiding truncation errors after considering the vertical grid spacing and maximum expected updraft velocities (Ziegler et al. 1983; Conway and Zrnić 1993). Terminal velocities are updated at each time step and new positions are calculated until the hailstone trajectory intersects the ground. 3D wind fields are not temporally adjusted or spatially shifted according to storm motion between radar scans as the temporal resolution of radar scans (~ 6 min. volumes) was deemed sufficient to capture the evolution of the wind field for hailstones with significant durations aloft. Nearest-neighbour interpolation is used to interpolate 3D wind grid values to exact hailstone positions. Once hailstones hit the ground, variables such as initial diameter, final diameter, initial position, final position, impact velocity and trajectory duration are stored. Two analyses are then derived from all simulated hailstone

impacts, 1) a maximum hail size swath, and 2) a cumulative kinetic energy field (KE_H). KE_H calculations are formalised below:

$$KE_H = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{2} m_i V_i^2 = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{12} \pi \rho d_i^3 (u_i^2 + v_i^2 + w_i^2), \quad (6)$$

where m is hailstone mass, ρ is hailstone density, d is hailstone equivolume diameter, n is amount of hailstone impacts within each grid square and the subscript i represents the i th hailstone impact within each grid square. Equation 6 underestimates the total kinetic energy of hail impacts as only a single, maximum size hailstone is initialised per voxel/grid point, per radar scan. Accordingly, we normalise KE_H values between 0 and 1 to indicate that this statistic should be interpreted as a ‘storm-specific’ measure, and should only be used to highlight regions with the most intense hailfall within an event. A 3×3 median filter is employed to reduce speckle noise and increase readability in maximum size and KE_H swaths (Lakshmanan et al. 2013).

f. Model Validation

Conventional radar-based hail impact swaths based on hail detections aloft (MESH, H_{DR} and vertical maximum reflectivity) are calculated in this study to compare with trajectory-based swaths. Maximum values for each parameter are accumulated on a 1 km grid throughout the lifetime of each storm. However, the temporal resolution of radar volumes (~ 6 min.) introduces spatial discontinuities between consecutive radar scans due to storm motion. A cell tracking technique was used to identify and match cells between radar scans in order to interpolate discontinuous swaths spatially along the storm path. For more information on the cell identification and matching techniques used in this study, the reader is referred to Lakshmanan et al. (2009) and Dixon and Wiener (1993), respectively. Intermediate grid points between radar scan times are interpolated by shifting the cell at time t forwards, and the cell at time $t + 1$ backwards along the storm motion vector. The resulting value of the intermediate grid points is then a linear combination of the values at time t and $t + 1$, weighted by their temporal proximities. The result is a spatially contiguous hail swath capable of providing a robust comparison to the trajectory-based swaths calculated in this study.

Insurance data were used as a validation dataset for the occurrence of damaging hail due to a lack of hail reports. Hail-related insurance claims were provided by Suncorp Insurance and are collated into daily 1 km grids comprising the number of insurance claims and the number of contracts. Refer to Warren et al. (2019) for more details on the Suncorp Insurance dataset. The extent of damaging hail was estimated by creating a binary damage grid (1 for

hail damage, 0 for no damage, -1 for no data), and a damage intensity metric was defined as the percentage of insurance contracts that made hail-related damage claims during the event. Various hail size thresholds were tested for each hail size estimation method to determine the strongest correlation with damaging hail at the corresponding grid points. If the swath value at a point exceeds the threshold, a positive prediction was made and if the value was less than the threshold, a negative prediction was made. By comparing these predictions to the actual binary insurance grid, contingency tables were developed containing true positives, false positives, false negatives and true negatives. The probability of detection (POD), false alarm rate (FAR), critical success index (CSI) and Heidke Skill Score (HSS) statistics were derived from the contingency tables for each method and the optimum threshold for each was defined by producing the highest HSS (Schaefer 1990; Doswell et al. 1990).

3. Case Study: 27/11/2014 Brisbane, Australia

In this section we apply the trajectory model to a case study from 27 November 2014, in Brisbane, Australia. The storm followed a northerly path through the densely populated Brisbane Metropolitan Area between 15:00 - 18:00 (LT; UTC+10:00), generating an estimated \$1.54 billion AUD in insurance losses and roughly 7000 hail related claims in the Suncorp Insurance dataset (Insurance Council of Australia 2017). These significant financial impacts are a result of strong surface level winds (39 ms^{-1} gusts), giant hailstones (~ 70 mm) and the timing of the event (weekday during the evening rush hour) (Rumsewicz 2015). Dual-Doppler data are sourced from two S-band radars, the Mt Stapylton operational weather radar and the CP-2 dual-polarisation research radar (1.0° and 0.93° halfpower beam-widths, respectively; Protat and Soderholm 2020). All hail retrievals are performed using the CP-2 radar due to its polarimetric capabilities. Atmospheric inputs to the melting model are sourced from a 10:00 LT sounding at Brisbane Airport (YBBN, ~ 10 km NE of Brisbane CBD). For the case study analysis in this section, only the H_{DR} hail size retrieval is applied. Comparison between the three hail detection methods is discussed in Section 4.

To further illustrate the HailTrack methodology, Figure 2 shows three selected 17 mm hailstones initiated close to the updraft at 16:42 LT during the 2014 Brisbane hailstorm. These examples have been included to note the effects of assumptions within the model and to demonstrate the importance of trajectory modelling for estimating hail advection. Firstly, trajectory A in Figure 2 transects the updraft through the lower levels whilst advecting towards the northwest. This hailstone is partially suspended whilst traversing the updraft, increasing its residence time below the melting level and allowing it to develop a $\sim 20\%$ larger meltwater fraction than trajectories B and C. This

FIG. 2. Trajectories of three 17 mm hailstones inserted within the updraft region of the Brisbane case study at 16:42 LT. Cross sections of vertical wind speed are taken along the dotted lines in three dimensional space. Filled circles represent hailstone positions at each trajectory step and are shaded according to meltwater fraction.

favourable melting trajectory demonstrates that even hailstones at the minimum initial size threshold (17 mm) do not melt completely in this case study. Trajectory A also shows that hailstones observed at low elevations (~ 3 km altitude in this case) may advect considerable distances in the presence of strong low level winds. Trajectory B is initiated in the updraft at an altitude of 7 km. This hailstone exhibits what is known as a ‘recirculating’ trajectory where hailstones cross the updraft on multiple occasions (Paluch 1978; Foote and Frank 1983; Conway and Zrnić 1993). Trajectory modelling by Paluch (1978) showed that the existence of this trajectory type is highly dependent on the microphysical environment within the updraft region. This is due to the fact that small hailstones entering an updraft with high super-cooled liquid water content will likely grow too large to be carried upwards and recirculate. The microphysical modelling within HailTrack only considers hailstone melting, which limits our confidence for such trajectories that may be strongly affected by hail growth. This limitation highlights that the intended use of HailTrack is to simulate the trajectories and fall out locations of hailstones once they have grown close to their maximum diameter. Equivalently, trajectories from a hailstorm that is still undergoing large amounts of growth at the time of radar observation will likely be simulated more accurately in subsequent radar scans.

Trajectory C in Figure 2 is initiated at an 11 km altitude within the updraft. Strong southwesterly winds associated with updraft divergence advected the hailstone into a downdraft region roughly 5 km to the east. Here, the hailstone descends sharply before encountering the low level southeasterly winds also observed in trajectory A. This analysis indicates that the wind profile in this updraft region is veering strongly with increased height. The resulting hailstone impact locations are separated by up to 8 km, which highlights why a uniform spatial shift is unlikely to capture the full complexity of hailstone advection. To further this point, the difference between initial and final positions are used to quantify the magnitude and direction of hailstone advection for all hailstones initiated using H_{DR} retrievals during this event. Advection vectors for all simulated hailstones are shown in Figure 3. The model predicts that small hailstones can advect large distances greater than 9 km. Figure 3 also shows that large hailstones capable of damaging buildings and structures can advect up to 6 km away from their initial locations aloft. These results show evidence of size sorting within the model as wind forcing has a disparate effect on hailstones depending on their size. Sorting causes a gradient in hail diameters across hail swaths and this has been observed in a range of observational studies (Ryzhkov et al. 2005; Kumjian and Ryzhkov 2008, 2012; Dawson et al. 2014). The broad distribution

FIG. 3. Hail advection calculated by the difference between the initial and final horizontal position of each modelled hailstone initiated using H_{DR} hail size retrievals. Advection plots are split between HSDA size categories with the number of hailstones in each category shown in the title. Radial labels represent the advection magnitude in kilometres. Individual hailstone points are coloured and plotted in order of their sizes.

of advection vectors within size classes also indicates that advection is heavily dependent on the spatio-temporal path taken by the hailstones through the 3D wind field. Advection in this storm occurs predominantly in a northwesterly direction relative to the surface. There is very little advection towards the south, which is consistent with the overall northerly storm motion.

It may be feasible to estimate a storm-wide advection correction by finding the average of all advection vectors modelled in the storm. The result in this case is 2100 m magnitude at a bearing of N 30° W. The storm's overall northerly path means hail advected approximately 40° to the left of the mean storm motion vector. Previous studies have attempted to draw a causal relationship between the overall advection correction vector and the underlying storm dynamics (Schiesser 1990; Schmid et al. 1992; Schuster et al. 2006). These explanations depend on storms exhibiting a quasi-stationary, supercellular structure where storm dynamics are well understood. The storm investigated here is categorised well by Nelson (1987) as a hybrid multicell-supercell storm. This classification is evidenced by a large elevated hail core (high reflectivity > 65 dBZ, differential reflectivity < 0 db), concurrent bounded weak echo regions and multiple short-lived ve-

locity couplets throughout the lifetime of the storm. Refer to Soderholm et al. (2017) for a more detailed radar-based analysis of this case study. This classification precludes any robust, qualitative comparison to previous storm dynamics literature. Furthermore, despite a large number of northwesterly advection vectors, hail advection may not be accurately characterised by a single spatial offset vector in this case as the hail swath is widened on both edges of the storm.

Another novel aspect of the trajectory model in this study is the ability to investigate the impact angle of hailstones. Impact angles are defined as the angle between the hailstone's impact velocity vector and the vertical. Figure 4 shows the distributions of impact angles within HSDA size categories. Hailstones that encountered gaps in the wind field (see Section 2c) are excluded from this figure. This was done to ensure the impact angles presented result from interactions with direct wind field retrievals and not gap-filled estimates. Both the mean and standard deviation of the approximately Gaussian distribution of impact angles decrease with increasing hail size. This is due to the terminal velocities of large hailstones having a more significant influence on impact velocity vectors. The importance of hail impact angles is noted in studies based on

FIG. 4. Frequency histograms for impact angles of the three HSDA size categories for all modelled hailstones using H_{DR} hail size retrievals. Impact angles are measured as the angle between the impact velocity vector and the surface normal vector. An impact angle of 0° indicates a perpendicular impact relative to the surface.

building damage due to hail (Hohl et al. 2002; Brown et al. 2015). Low impact angles limit hail damage to mostly roofing, whereas high impact angles increase the potential for siding and window damage to structures. Furthermore, large horizontal velocity components associated with high impact angles increase the magnitude of the total impact velocity. The addition of horizontal velocity components in this study increased the average estimated impact velocities by 22%; however, this is highly weighted by smaller sizes due to their prevalence in the model. Discriminating into HSDA size categories reveals that the addition of horizontal velocities increases the average impact magnitude by 25% for small hailstones, 18% for large hailstones, and only 4% for giant hailstones. To the authors' knowledge no observational studies have investigated the impact angles of natural hail, preventing a comparison of these results to existing literature. This, along with the aforementioned problems involved with retrieving low-level wind fields from radar data limit the confidence level for the results shown in Figure 4. Nevertheless, we have included these results as a step towards more accurately estimating the potential impacts of hail in the presence of strong low-level winds using remote sensing methods.

In addition to mapping hailfall for historical events, the forward trajectory approach used here can also be applied to generate short-term predictions of hailfall. The lead time of these short-term nowcasts is reliant on both the simulated trajectory durations and the computational efficiency of the model. For a ten second trajectory time step ($\Delta t = 10$ s), the current software implementation of HailTrack processes an operational radar volume (>10000 trajectories in this case) in less than 20 s, making it suitable for nowcasting without the need for parallel processing. An example of a nowcast created for the Brisbane 2014 hailstorm using all radar volumes up until 16:42 local time is given in Figure 5. This figure illustrates the immediate hail risk with roughly 10-15 minutes lead time. Each point on the figure represents a hail impact, with colours indicating the expected time until

impact and point sizes varying proportionally to impact diameters. Although the lead time of such a nowcast may be too short for most conventional nowcasting applications, the specificity of these warnings may reduce the number of false alarms commonly associated with hail nowcasts. The trajectory model can therefore potentially assist decision-making around hail risk in the minutes leading up to hail events.

4. HailTrack Verification

The hailfall estimates made in this study are predominantly verified using insurance loss data due to the small number of hail size reports. Although they are an extremely valuable source of validation, there are many factors that can undermine the reproducibility of insurance damage claims between different storm events. Briefly, these include but are not limited to: 1) the spatial density and value of insured assets, 2) the extent of shielding (e.g. from other buildings and trees), 3) the type and age of building components, 4) the extent and size of the damage, 5) other damage types (intense rainfall, severe wind gusts), 6) wind speed and direction, 7) hailstone size and density and 8) whether contract holders reliably file claims for every instance of damage. Despite these limitations, insurance data has been noted to provide a valuable insight into the extent of damaging hail at the surface, which makes it a suitable choice for validating the results in this study (Hohl et al. 2002; Brown et al. 2015; Warren et al. 2019).

Table 1 contains skill scores calculated by comparing each hail retrieval method to a binary representation of insurance damage as discussed in Section 2. Three retrievals without trajectory corrections are included in this table and are referred to as 'conventional' swaths throughout this section. Of the three conventional swaths, a vertical-maximum reflectivity threshold of 64 dBZ is the most skillful predictor of binary insurance damage with a HSS of 0.50. Uncorrected MESH and H_{DR} swaths showed slightly

FIG. 5. An example of a potential nowcast from HailTrack calculated after the 16:42 LT radar scan. Points on the graph indicate the position of modelled hail impacts, these are shaded according to the time in minutes until hail impact plotted in ascending order. Negative numbers indicate hail that has already fallen before 16:42 LT and positive numbers show the how long after 16:42 LT hail currently aloft is expected to land.

lower HSS values of 0.46 and 0.48 respectively. There is a consensus among previous studies that the optimal MESH threshold for predicting severe hail occurrence (≥ 25 mm) in a similar spatio-temporal proximity to a storm is around 30 mm (Wilson et al. 2009; Cintineo et al. 2012; Ortega 2018; Murillo and Homeyer 2019; Warren et al. 2019). In this study a MESH threshold of 46 mm showed the most skill for identifying regions with hail related insurance damage. The significant difference in optimal thresholds from previous studies highlights the alternate methodology used here. Instead of matching hail reports to either a single, spatio-temporally representative value for an entire storm or within a pre-defined neighbourhood radius, we point-match radar-based swaths to a spatial grid. Warren et al. (2019) highlighted the effects of these matching methodologies by showing that the optimum MESH threshold changed from 44 mm to 32 mm when increasing the neighbourhood radius used to construct contingency tables from 0 km (i.e. grid-scale comparisons) to 5 km. Both the difference in matching techniques and the type of ground truth mean that skill scores for the conventional swaths in Table 1 cannot be reliably compared to previous

literature; instead, they have been included to demonstrate the benefit of applying the trajectory model in this study.

HailTrack HSDA hail size retrievals produced the only trajectory modelled swath that did not outperform the conventional swaths. A large 69 mm optimum hail size threshold led to a reasonable probability of detection (0.53) but is outweighed by a similarly high false alarm ratio (0.45), resulting in a relatively poor Heidke Skill Score (0.46). As discussed previously, this hail retrieval method requires a prescribed maximum hail size for ‘giant’ HSDA classifications and it is possible that this assumption plays a significant role in the skill scores observed. The sensitivity of the HSDA retrieval method to the prescribed 75 mm maximum size threshold was explored by varying threshold values between 55-85 mm. These sensitivity experiments showed only small fluctuations in the skill scores (< 0.01), indicating that the accuracy of the HSDA retrieval method is not strongly influenced by the maximum hail size assumption. Instead, we find that the poor skill of the HSDA method is a result of overestimating the amount ‘giant’ classifications, especially in the earlier stages of storm development. This results in a significant amount of ‘giant’

TABLE 1. Skill scores for each hail detection method used in this study. The optimum threshold is defined by the highest Heidke Skill Score (HSS).

Hail Retrieval	Threshold	POD	FAR	CSI	HSS	Description
Reflectivity	64 dBZ	0.53	0.39	0.40	0.50	Reflectivity swath interpolated by tracking cell movement
MESH	46 mm	0.46	0.38	0.36	0.46	MESH swath interpolated by tracking cell movement
H _{DR}	37 mm	0.47	0.36	0.37	0.48	H _{DR} swath interpolated by tracking cell movement
HailTrack MESH	24 mm	0.50	0.35	0.39	0.50	MESH swath corrected using trajectory modelling
HailTrack H _{DR}	37 mm	0.60	0.33	0.46	0.58	H _{DR} swath corrected using trajectory modelling
HailTrack HSDA	69 mm	0.53	0.45	0.37	0.46	H _{DR} weighted HSDA swath corrected using trajectory modelling

hail in areas with no observed insurance damage, leading to a high false alarm rate and poor skill scores.

Conventional MESH and H_{DR} hail swaths improved considerably when HailTrack advection corrections were applied, with HSS values increasing from 0.46 to 0.50 and 0.48 to 0.58, respectively. The optimum MESH threshold changed from 46 mm to 24 mm before and after the HailTrack corrections were applied, due to the reflectivity scaling used to extend MESH into three dimensions. The corrected MESH skill score is consistent with Warren et al. (2019) who found HSS values between 0.49 - 0.51 by using a neighbourhood radius of 5 - 7 km to account for hailstone advection. The corrected MESH swath also outperforms the conventional H_{DR} swath, indicating that trajectory-corrections to single polarised hail swaths can outperform conventional polarimetric hail swaths. The HailTrack H_{DR} method shows that combining dual-polarised retrievals and trajectory corrections produces the most accurate hailfall estimates. The skill scores of this method considerably outperform other methods tested in this study. All subsequent trajectory modelling and verification in this study is initiated with H_{DR} hail size retrievals as they demonstrate the highest correlation with ground truth.

Impacts swaths from the trajectory model are derived by collating impact positions and sizes from all hailstone trajectory simulations. Figure 6 shows both a maximum estimated hail size swath and an accumulated kinetic energy swath with a 1×1 km horizontal grid spacing. The maximum size swath indicates a period of weak multicell convection to the southwest of Jimboomba with patchy, short-lived hailfall. There are also two contiguous hailstreaks from separate storms that followed a northerly path

through the town of Fernvale and the city of Brisbane. These swaths retain spatial continuity despite the discrete temporal nature of the underlying radar data. This is a result of simulating hailstone trajectories from all elevations and from previous radar scans.

Three hail reports in the Bureau of Meteorology's severe storms database were collected for the 27 November 2014 Brisbane hailstorm. Figure 6 shows close (<5 mm) agreement between hail size reports and the corresponding values on the maximum hail size swath for the two reports in the 30 mm - 50 mm range. However, the remaining 70 mm hail report is under-estimated by the model with a size prediction of around 50 mm. This is a result of the H_{DR} - hail size relationship underestimating the prevalence of giant hail in this case. The H_{DR} relationship was developed using only 86 hail reports during a Colorado hailstorm on 03/06/02. There were only two reports greater than 55 mm in diameter in this data set; as a result, the relationship is undercalibrated for predicting hail sizes this large. The ability of H_{DR} to estimate giant hail sizes is further hindered by noting it is largely based on horizontal reflectivity. Z_H alone is useful for discerning small from large hail, but shows limited skill for discriminating between large and giant hail (Blair et al. 2011; Ryzhkov et al. 2013b). It should be noted that the prescribed HSDA maximum size (75 mm) and the maximum MESH value (76 mm) more accurately predicted the maximum hail size reported for this storm (~70 mm).

The accumulated kinetic energy swath in Figure 6 highlights a smaller region of particularly intense hailfall. The hail core of the storm passed directly over this region resulting in a large number of large/giant hailstones in a small

Fig. 6. a) Accumulated maximum hail size estimates and b) accumulated hail kinetic energy for the 2014 Brisbane hailstorm between 15:48-17:30 LT. Unfilled circles show the position and size in millimetres of BoM hail reports and triangles indicate the positions of radars (CP-2 research radar on the left and the operational Mt. Stapylton radar on the right).

area. Kinetic energy accumulations are also influenced by the storm's motion, low-level wind speed and the vertical extent of the hail core. The kinetic energy swath provides a valuable indication of where the most intense hailfall has occurred, which in this case does not match precisely with where the largest hail fell. It is important to note that only one hailstone is simulated for each H_{DR} radar voxel. The true kinetic energy distribution is likely heavily influenced by the number concentration of large hail within individual voxels. Once again, kinetic energy estimates in this study are used only as a *relative* measure of the intensity of hailfall and not as a quantitative prediction of the true accumulated kinetic energy values at the ground.

Figure 7 illustrates the correlation between HailTrack-predicted hailfall and insurance data by superimposing maximum hail size and kinetic energy swaths onto hail-related claims. The spatial bounds of Figure 7 are limited to the main Brisbane hailstreak as there is very little insurance coverage and no hail related claims outside of this region (due, in part, to lower population density). The spatial extent of hail related damage is captured well by the hail size contours in Figure 7a, with the exception of a small amount of hail damage on the western edge of the damage swath. The kinetic energy 'hotspot' region also correlates well with the highest hail damage percentages, as shown in Figure 7b. The southern extent of the kinetic energy contours appear to overestimate the relative hail intensity, although there is a large number of grid points with no insurance data in this region. An attempt was made to quantify the relationship between the predicted

and observed hail intensities. A point-matched linear regression between the accumulated kinetic energy field and damage percentage field (not shown) yields an r^2 value of 0.55. This indicates a weak positive correlation between accumulated kinetic energy and the percentage of contracts with damage claims. There is potential to improve this damage intensity relationship by weighting variables such as diameter or impact velocity, or by introducing new variables such as the impact angle of hailstone impacts as wind-driven hail likely causes more severe damage (e.g. Richter et al. 2014).

The correlation between the maximum hail size swath and binary insurance grid in Figure 7a is explored further by finding the most skillful hail size threshold for predicting hail damage. An array of hail size thresholds from 0 to 50 mm were tested and the critical success index (CSI) scores for each of these calculations are shown in Figure 8. CSI scores for the conventional, radar-derived H_{DR} swath are also shown to highlight the benefit of deriving advection corrected swaths from the trajectory model. The corrected H_{DR} swath largely outperforms the conventional H_{DR} swath for nearly all hail size thresholds. The optimum thresholds for the conventional swath and corrected swath are identical (37 mm), but the corrected swath has a significantly higher optimum CSI score (0.46 compared to 0.37 for the conventional swath). This improvement is largely attributed to modelling hailstone advection. Similar skill score improvements were also observed for MESH retrievals (Table 1).

Fig. 7. a) Contours of the accumulated maximum hail size swath plotted over a binary representation of hail damage from the 27 November 2014 Brisbane hailstorm. Grid boxes with no insurance data are marked as ‘Unknown’, boxes with contracts but no damage claims as ‘No damage’ and boxes with damage claims as ‘Damage’. b) Contours of normalised accumulated kinetic energy shown over the percentage of contracts that incurred hail claims.

Figure 9 further illustrates the improvement in damage forecast skill derived from modelling hail trajectories. The conventional H_{DR} swath in panel a) exhibits a clear spatial offset from the insurance damage swath as hailstones are detected aloft before they are advected westward. Figure 9b shows this spatial offset is mostly removed from the corrected swath as it is well aligned with the insurance damage swath. Figure 3 showed that hailstones advected predominantly to the northwest and accounting for this motion significantly improves the correlation with surface damage. The HailTrack swath is also up to 7 km wider than the conventional swath as a result of hail advection. The poorest correlation is located on the meridional extremities of the damage swath. Sensitivity tests (not shown) indicate that decreasing the threshold size would encompass these regions but it would also result in a higher false alarm rate, especially in regions south of the two radars. The trajectory-modelled H_{DR} swath already appears to overestimate the presence of damaging hail in the southern part of the Figure 9 domain though it is difficult to assess whether these inaccuracies stem from HailTrack modelling assumptions, initial hail size estimates or the aforementioned observational limitations involved with insurance claims.

In order to test the sensitivity of HailTrack to micro-physical modelling assumptions, five additional simulations were performed (settings reported in Table 2). Each of these experiments either varied the environmental temperature or the density of hailstones in the model. The control experiment contains the variable density profile outlined in Equation 4 and the temperature profile from an environmental sounding. Control experiment settings were used in all of the results presented earlier. Impact estimates created using control settings employed an optimal hail size threshold of 37 mm to create an impact swath 557 km² in area, and achieved a HSS of 0.58. The maximum change in diameter due to melting observed in the control experiment was 7 mm, and the maximum velocity and kinetic energy of individual hailstones in this experiment were 41.7 ms⁻¹ and 52.9 J respectively. Throughout the additional experiments, hailstone melting was enhanced by lower hailstone densities and higher environmental temperatures. Table 2 shows that enhanced hailstone melting lowers impact quantities such as impact velocity and kinetic energy, and the opposite is true for experiments with reduced hailstone melting.

Microphysical changes can potentially affect the accuracy of hail swaths by altering the amount of advection experienced by hailstones. Changes in density and melt-

FIG. 8. A Roebber performance diagram for the radar-derived maximum hail size swath and the trajectory model-derived hail size swath. Each method has a separate line on the plot and each dot represents a separate threshold for that method (refer to colourbar for threshold value). CSI skill scores are contoured and labelled in black and the point with the highest CSI value for each method is annotated.

TABLE 2. Results of microphysical sensitivity tests. Six model runs initiated with H_{DR} hail sizes were performed for the 2014 Brisbane hailstorm with differing model settings: control (variable density, measured temperature), low density ($600 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), high-density ($917 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), $+10^\circ\text{C}$ temperature profile, -10°C temperature profile and no melting. Various parameters of interest are shown for each model setting.

Experiment	Control	Low Density	High Density	$+10^\circ\text{C}$	-10°C	No Melt
Min. Dia. (mm)	7	2	8	0	14	16
Max. Dia. (mm)	57	49	57	53	60	61
Max. Melt (mm)	9	15	9	21	2	0
Max. V (ms^{-1})	41.7	39.1	41.7	41.8	41.5	40.41
Max. KE (J)	52.9	15.2	52.9	41.6	58.3	55.2
Small Adv. (m)	10200	13400	9400	10400	10500	11400
Large Adv. (m)	6000	7500	6000	5400	6700	7800
Giant Adv. (m)	3900	-	3900	1600	4000	4300
Threshold (mm)	37.2	31.5	37.2	34.7	38.8	39.6
Swath Area (km^2)	557	537	554	504	593	595
HSS	0.58	0.59	0.58	0.58	0.57	0.57

ing characteristics can alter hailstone terminal velocities, and subsequently hail advection magnitudes. In particular, small and large hail in the low density experiment showed much higher advection magnitudes compared to the control experiment. This resulted in a slightly higher Heidke

Skill Score by encompassing more insurance damage on the outer edges of the predicted hail damage swath. The increased skill of the low density experiment indicates that the wind retrieval method may be underestimating the true velocity of storm-driven winds, resulting in an underesti-

FIG. 9. a) A binary representation of insurance damage as in Figure 7 overlaid with a grid of outlined cells containing radar derived HDR swath values greater than 37 mm. b) Same as panel a) except using a trajectory model-derived HDR swath.

mate of the amount of advection for the control experiment. The damage prediction skill for the remaining experiments are similar despite the microphysical changes, as the optimum hail size threshold adjusted according to the amount of melting. Lower optimum hail size thresholds were found in experiments with enhanced melting, and higher thresholds were found for experiments with reduced melting. This shows that the spatial accuracy of HailTrack swaths for a single event are insensitive to the hail melting model, and that the improved accuracy of HailTrack is predominantly a result of estimating hail advection in this case. The melting model may play a more important role when attempting to find an optimum hail size threshold between events with disparate thermodynamic environments. As such, further testing between events with varied thermodynamic environments is required to fully quantify the role of the melting model within HailTrack. Additional insurance validation datasets for severe hailstorms will enable this testing in the future.

5. Summary and Future Directions

This study introduced HailTrack, a novel methodology aimed at improving radar-based hail impact estimates. Radar retrievals were used to estimate hail size and position aloft, before trajectory simulations were run to predict

where hailstones will impact the ground. Three radar-based hail size retrievals (MESH, H_{DR} , hybrid $H_{DR}/HSDA$) were tested to initiate trajectories and a dual-Doppler, three dimensional wind field was used to model hailstone advection. A thermodynamic melting model was also coupled with trajectory simulations to reflect the changing size and terminal velocities of hailstones below the melting level.

We applied the model to a case study in Brisbane, Australia that produced >70 mm hail and over \$1.5 billion AUD in insured losses. The model showed that hailstones may advect up to 9 km away from their initial positions due to strong winds in hail producing regions of the storm. Smaller hailstones were shown to advect further and impact more horizontally than larger hailstones due to their smaller terminal velocities. Hailstone advection in this storm occurred predominantly in a northwesterly cardinal direction, and $\sim 40^\circ$ to the left of the bulk storm motion vector. Spatially-continuous, advection-corrected hail impact swaths were derived by collating maximum hail sizes and accumulating kinetic energy estimates. A trajectory-based nowcast was also noted to produce lead times of around 10-15 minutes.

Hail-related insurance claims were used to verify the model-derived hail swaths. Model-derived swaths using MESH and H_{DR} retrievals significantly outperformed the corresponding conventional swaths. H_{DR} hail size re-

trievals showed the highest skill for predicting one or more insurance claims within a 1×1 km area, with an optimum >37 mm H_{DR} threshold. Further, we showed that model-derived H_{DR} swaths outperform conventional H_{DR} swaths for the vast majority of viable threshold values. A hail-fall intensity parameter was created by accumulating the kinetic energy of hailstone impacts; this parameter showed a weak linear correlation to the percentage of insurance contracts that experienced hail damage. The accuracy of model predictions was found to be insensitive to changes in hailstone density or the temperature profile of the atmosphere. This indicates that model-derived swaths outperform conventional swaths predominantly due to advection corrections, independent of the microphysical modelling.

Future work should also involve extending the model validation in this study to a larger sample size of hail events. This research is currently limited by a lack of ground truth data, which highlights the need for improved hail observations and further collaboration with the insurance industry. In the future, we aim to extend the lead time of HailTrack nowcasts by applying the model to storms advected forward in time or by adding an existing parameterization of hail growth (e.g. Paluch 1978; Ziegler et al. 1983). Lastly, the applicability of the trajectory modelling approach could be greatly improved by removing the requirement for dual-Doppler radar coverage. To this end, future studies should investigate the accuracy of hail trajectories calculated using single Doppler wind retrievals.

Data availability statement. Public access to the insurance dataset used in this study is restricted due to proprietary agreements with Suncorp Insurance. All radiosonde and radar data have been made freely available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3600107>.

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